

Deliverable D5

Title

Calibration procedure for testing machine to close the traceability chain for dynamic forces across a frequency range of 0 Hz to 1000 Hz including a template calibration certificate which can be used for forces in the range of 1 N to 1 MN.

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

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Leading partner

Arnd Nitschke (USTUTT)

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